

EMPIRICAL APPROACH TO STUDYING THE PROBLEM OF MOTIVATION

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It is known that certain methods are chosen to prove the hypothesis put forward in the research. The process of choosing psychological methods is considered a creative process of the researcher, and it should fully cover the part of the research subject that we need to study [2], [3]. The results obtained through our chosen methods should be sufficient to prove (or, conversely, disprove) the research hypothesis. The following psychological methods were selected according to the hypothesis indicated in our study.

1. Observation method. With the help of the observation method, the characteristics of learning motives are systematically studied in a number of lessons in the experimental and control classes based on a special program, and the data are recorded in a special diary.
2. Interview method. It served to clarify the results of the observation and determine the direction of the further diagnostic process.
3. Psychodiagnostic methods:
 - a) Questionnaire "Motives of study activity" (A.K. Markova);
 - b) Questionnaire "Needs for success" (Y.M. Orlov);
 - v) "Determining students' attitudes to educational activities" (A.A. Rean and V.A. Yakovlev) methodology;
 - g) Questionnaire "Motivation to study at an educational institution" (T.I. Ilina);
 - d) Situational test "Triple comparison to determine the superiority of external and internal learning motive" (T. Pushkina).

These standardized and experimental tests have been translated into Uzbek and are adapted for students of academic lyceums and vocational colleges.

In a psychological-pedagogical experiment, the training system developed by us was tested. In the experiment, according to the training program, the students' activity of the following study activity motives was developed: re-consolidation of knowledge, the ability to ask questions, the ability to participate in and hold a discussion, and to create a system of reasons for the formation of creative thinking in students.

First of all, it is worth mentioning briefly about the types of diagnostic methods. In general, "the tools used by modern psychodiagnostics are divided into the

following groups according to their quality: highly formalized methods or strictly formalized methods" [1,23].

Rigorous formalized methods include tests, questionnaires, projective technique methods and psychophysiological methods. Such methods are characterized by the qualities of certain regulation, objectivity of the research process, standardization, reliability and validity.

Less formal methods include observation, conversation and interview, analysis of activity products, and these methods provide important information about the subjects being studied.

It is wrong to contrast these two categories of methodologies. This is because they usually complement each other. A complete diagnostic study requires a harmonious balance of one or another method.

The observation method is considered one of the ancient methods of psychological diagnosis, with the help of which it is possible to obtain multifaceted information about a person.

Observation is also of two types: casual observation and scientific observation. Scientific observation as a psychodiagnostic method is related to problem setting, selection of situations for observation, determination of psychological qualities, developed system of observation and recording of results. In other words, observation as a method has a purpose and a scheme.

According to its purpose, observation is divided into searching observation and concrete observation. The goal of exploratory observation is to obtain a complete description of the aspects and relationships specific to a given problem.

If the purpose of observation is concrete and clear, in such cases it is limited only to the selection of necessary facts and events. In this case, the objective content of the observation is determined in advance (what should be observed) and the observed phenomenon is divided into certain units.

Regardless of the nature of surveillance, it is necessary for the observer to have a certain surveillance program, action plan. The observation scheme consists of a number of observation units, the method and form of describing the observed psychological phenomenon. Before observation, it is necessary to isolate certain aspects of behavior from the general picture, individual acts that can be directly observed.

Interview method. This method of collecting primary data is based on verbal communication. If certain rules are observed, this method allows to collect relatively reliable information about future events, stable trends, and motives of this or that behavior.

It would be wrong to think that interviewing is the easiest method. The requirements of the "art" of conversation are strict. He needs to get into the heart of the interlocutor (interviewer), to justify his trust, to be able to get sincere and honest answers.

Conversation as a psychodiagnostic method is divided into several types according to its character and form. One of the most common types of conversation is an interview. An interview is a conversation carried out on the basis of a certain plan, and relies on the direct communication (contact) of the interviewer with the respondent (testee). According to the form of the interview: free (an interview based on the general program, but without distinguishing the specific details of the issues); standardized (an interview with a strict strategy and tactics, with all activities developed in detail, with a fixed order of questions, with developed answer options); is divided into partially standardized (conversation with a strict strategy, but relatively free tactics).

According to the nature of the interview, it is divided into diagnostic and clinical types. Diagnostic interview is a method of collecting information with a general content, in which information is collected about the motives of the respondent's behavior, the world of motivation of the person, and the reasons for his decisions. A clinical interview is considered a method of therapeutic conversation and serves to help the recipient to overcome his problems, internal conflicts, conflicts with others.

Taking into account the above, the interview we conducted to study the motivation of academic activities of students of academic lyceum and vocational colleges is partially a standardized and diagnostic interview.

We tried to meet the following methodological requirements during the interview with students:

- we tried to create a warm, fully understanding situation in order to ensure a positive atmosphere in the communication with the student;
- we denied the way to create an artificial environment aimed at getting a favorable answer from the student;
- we managed to create an environment of mutual trust where the student can freely express his mental state;
- discussing, approving or denying the student's position, taking into account his personal opinions.

Thus, we tried to prove the suitability of the psychological methods designed for experimental research above to achieve the research goals. Now we will directly start the empirical analysis of the results of the experimental research.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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